

COURSE CLUSTERING BASED ON THE PHYLOGENIC TREE OF STUDENTS' GRADES IN ARCHITECTURAL DEGREE (RESEARCH)

Daniel García-Escudero¹

ETSAB-UPC

Barcelona, Spain

0000-0001-6259-1094

Berta Bardí-Milà²

ETSAB-UPC

Barcelona, Spain

0000-0003-0271-670X

Francesc Fayos³

ETSAB-UPC

Barcelona, Spain

0000-0002-0837-7369

Francesc Valls⁴

ETSAB-UPC

Barcelona, Spain

0000-0002-9400-5659

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ABSTRACT

A large-scale correlational analysis was conducted on the grades of the students who completed their studies in the 1994 curriculum in the Barcelona School of Architecture. The study included the passing grades of a total of 3910 students corresponding to all 47 compulsory subjects, as elective courses were excluded. The objective of the research was to explore whether courses with related content were associated with the corresponding grades at an aggregate level, and identify similarities and dissimilarities in their clustering. The correlation between the grades in all courses was computed pairwise, and used as a distance measure to quantify the grade of affinity between them. Using this distance metric, the results were processed using hierarchical cluster analysis producing a tree structure according to this similarity/dissimilarity measure. The clustering results were visualized in a phylogenetic tree, identifying the optimal number of clusters and coloring the results accordingly. The visualization of this tree matched very closely the grouping of

¹ Daniel García-Escudero; DGE; daniel.garcia-escudero@upc.edu

² Berta Bardí-Milà; BBM; berta.bardi@upc.edu

³ Francisco Fayos Vallés; FFV; f.fayos@upc.edu

⁴ Francesc Valls; FVD; francesc.valls@upc.edu

courses according to departmental divisions, indicating a strong association between the grades obtained and specific areas of knowledge. The lowest marks were also found to be concentrated in the first years and among the graphic and design subjects. These results reinforce previous studies that have investigated the relationship between academic performance during the degree course and the entry grade. The great discontinuity between them and the fact that PBL is characteristic of the degree course and less common in secondary school could be the reasons for these results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Architecture studies have as their backbone the active methodology of Project Based Learning (PBL). "Learning by doing projects" connects with the methodology that is being implemented in the learning environments of early childhood and primary education cycles, and which is less frequently applied in secondary and higher education. Architecture studies are a prime example of how training is based, precisely, on practical workshops where designs are developed and integrate other disciplines such as construction, structural engineering, history or representation, and which involve skills such as teamwork, creativity, communication or social commitment. These design workshop courses do not have a parallel in secondary education, which causes a discontinuity between university admission scores and the grades obtained during university studies [1].

More specifically, the 1994 curriculum, which we analyze, was the first that include the course of Architectural Design in the first academic year. Unlike other schools, at the Barcelona School of Architecture (ETSAB-UPC) it was included from the first semester and was present until the capstone project in the fifth year. The course of "design" and its characteristic "architecture workshop" –understood as both the setting and teaching modality– becomes the most distinctive teaching practice within the studies, both in the beauxartian and the polytechnic traditions that began in the 19th century. Learning is not only "by projects", but "making projects", an aspect that defines the teaching-learning dynamics of the degree. However, this study is not restricted to the group of design courses, but contextualizes them within the framework of other technical and theory subjects, more related of humanistic studies, as well as science and polytechnic studies.

Therefore, based on previous studies that analyzed the low correlation between the university admission score and the grades throughout the career, we now focus on the relationship between the 47 compulsory subjects in the degree, which as explained before were very diverse. Specifically, the research questions are:

1. Is there any relationship between the different courses and the academic year in which they are taught? It could be assumed that the discontinuity between the learning methodologies prior to entering the degree and the different skills and abilities that are valued in Architecture (creative thinking, and design of

forms and spaces) should have an impact on the quantitative academic performance of the first years.

2. Is there any correlation between the courses that make up the 7 areas of knowledge in the curriculum: Construction, Composition, Physics, Mathematics, Urban and Territorial Planning, Architectural Design and Graphic Representation? It should be noted that, despite the fact that this plan was developed prior to Bologna and the process of homogenization of all university studies (which became degrees), the very polytechnic structure of the university in which the ETSAB is included already entails the inclusion of training activities and assessment systems common to all degrees, regardless of their particularities. This circumstance, in the field of Architecture and such heterogeneous curriculum, makes it especially relevant to analyze to what extent the diverse nature of the areas of knowledge correlates with the quantitative results of learning. A learning that also responds to PBL in some subjects, while others work with more classical, behavioral and passive approaches.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data processing

All data was processed using the R programming language [1] because of its wide availability of packages for data analysis [2], and following the principles of reproducible research [3].

Source data was stored as a Microsoft Excel file that contained 3910 records corresponding to the grades of the students that graduated within the 1994 Plan of Study in the Barcelona School of Architecture, excluding the elective courses. For each record, the passing grades of each of the 47 compulsory courses were stored as columns.

This data structure was not suitable for analysis, and following the principles of tidy data [4] where each variable should form a column and each observation should form a row, was converted from this “wide” format to a “long” format table structure, resulting in a table with 183,770 rows for each pair of student-course, and a column with their corresponding passing grades.

Because the collected data corresponded to compulsory courses that were a requirement to graduate, by definition there was not any missing data in the dataset. There were, however some grades that were below the passing grade of 5, because some grades above or equal to 4 could be “compensated” with higher grades in other courses.

2.2 Grade distribution

The mean of all the grades was 6.22, and the standard deviation was 1.12 grade points. The distribution was right-skewed with a moderately positive skew of 0.73. Since the normality could not be computed using the Shapiro–Wilk test because the sample size was larger than 500, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was used to check

the grade distribution against the normal distribution, resulting in a D value of almost 1 with a p-value very close to zero, rejecting the hypothesis that the grades were normally distributed.

The density of each of the 47 courses in the degree were plotted in a single chart to visualize their distributions, using the overall density plot corresponding to the combined grades in the whole degree as a reference (Fig. 1, left). The bandwidth of the smoothing kernel was 0.5, about half the standard deviation of the population, which was considered an adequate value of the uncertainty of the grades, as most grades clustered in increments of half a grade point in a 0 to 10 scale.

The results showed that the distribution of the grades in the degree does not follow a normal distribution, and that almost none of the grades obtained in the courses appear to be normally distributed. There is a large variation in the grade distributions per course, with some courses having a peak near the passing mark, and others almost symmetrically and normally distributed around the 6 to 7 marks.

To investigate this variation in the distributions, the courses were grouped according to the academic year where they belonged within the five years of the architecture degree, using the global distribution as a reference (Fig. 1, right), using the same bandwidth parameter as the previous figure. The results showed that the grades become progressively more normal in the later years, while the initial years concentrate most of their grades near the passing grade.

Fig. 1. Density plots for all 47 individual courses analyzed (left) and grouped according to their academic year (right), compared to the density plot of all the grades in the degree (overlaid as a dotted black line)

2.3 Correlations

The table of all grades was converted to a matrix, where each student was assigned to a row and the corresponding passing grades of each course were assigned to the columns, resulting in a 3910x47 matrix. The pairwise Pearson's correlation coefficient was computed for all pairs of columns using the *rcorr* function in the *Hmisc* R package. The function returned a symmetrical 47x47 matrix with the pairwise correlation coefficients, with ones in the diagonal as the grades in every

course were perfectly correlated with themselves. In addition to the correlation matrix, the function also returned a matrix with the asymptotic p-values required to compute the statistical significance for each pair of correlations.

The correlation values corresponding to a single triangle and excluding the diagonal were extracted and plotted as a combined histogram and density plot (Fig. 2, left), with the same value of 0.1 for both binwidth and bandwidth. The result show that almost all courses are positively correlated, but also that most of the correlations are very weak, with a range of -0.10 to 0.61, and a peak near the 0.1 value.

In addition, the correlations below the statistical significance threshold ($p < 0.05$) were overlaid with a cross. Interestingly the courses of “Structures II” (E I) and “Descriptive Geometry I” (GD I) showed a much higher number of non-statistically significant correlations than expected (Fig. 2, right), with 27 and 16 respectively, followed by “Sketching I” (D I) with 12. The mean number of non-significant correlations per course was 3.2.

Fig. 2. Combined histogram and density plot of the pairwise correlation between courses (left). Outstanding courses with more than 3 non-statistically significant correlations ($p > 0.05$) with any other courses in the degree (right)

2.4 Heatmap

Since the correlation matrix was difficult to interpret visually, the results were plotted as a heatmap using the *corrplot* R package (Fig. 3). The heatmap colors used diverging color scale using a cold-hot representation (red for lower values, gray for near-zero values, and blue for higher values), with most of the values appearing in light orange colors. This heatmap revealed that some course correlations exhibit clustering, which is directly observable in blocks of courses that share a similar name when sorted in alphabetical order, and is discussed in the following subsections.

Fig. 3. Pairwise correlations between courses from the passing grades of all 3910 students. Results below statistical significance ($p > 0.05$) are shown with a black cross overlaid

2.5 Distance metrics

The matrix of Pearson’s correlations was interpreted as distances using the *distanceMatrix* function in the *ClassDiscovery* R package, using the “pearson” metric with the following formula of distance between course i and course j .

$$distance(i, j) = \frac{1 - correlation(course_i, course_j)}{2}$$

Since the Pearson’s correlation has values in the $[-1, 1]$ range, this distance metric can only have values in the $[0, 1]$ range. The distances were stored in a 47×47 distance matrix, symmetric because $d_{ij} = d_{ji}$ and the diagonal was populated with null values to replace zero distances for the cases when $i=j$.

The representation of this distance matrix was produced with the *ph heatmap* R package, reordering the rows and columns according to the distance metric to place more affine courses together, separating clusters into rectangular partitions of the heatmap (Fig. 4), and placing a dendrogram at the margins of the heatmap.

Fig. 4. Distances computed from the Pearson's correlation with the cluster separation

2.6 Clusters

The distances in the matrix were clustered using agglomerative hierarchical clustering with the *hclust* function in the *stats* R package using the “ward.D” method. The results were visualized using the *fviz_dend* function in the *factoextra* R package (Fig. 5).

This tree-like representation allows partitioning the dendrogram into clusters according to their distance (height) to the “trunk”, summarizing multiple possible clustering results into a single diagram. In the case of the degree of architecture, the number of clusters chosen were 6, but from the figure it is clear that there is another possible partition around height=1 into two clusters, and around height=0.7 into four clusters. The distribution of the grades within the identified clusters was also plotted (Fig. 6) for comparison.

Fig. 5. Dendrogram representation of the results of the hierarchical clustering, depicting partitions into 2 clusters (dotted rectangles), 4 clusters (shaded rectangles), and 6 clusters (color labels)

Fig. 6. Distribution of the grades within the identified clusters

3 RESULTS

The results obtained through the discussed methodologies, point to three very specific conclusions:

First, as Fig. 1 shows, the correlation of grades across the degree shows a quantitative increase in the average grades as the years advance. Therefore, the discontinuity with prior pre-university training is confirmed, which may imply that adaptation to studies structurally based on PBL and with a great emphasis on creative abilities entails greater difficulty in passing the initial courses, despite that many of them are propaedeutic.

Second, the correlation between the 47 courses shows a grouping (dendrogram in Fig. 5) that practically reproduces the organization in the different areas of knowledge of the curriculum. Moreover, an analysis at a more global level allows us to organize them into two large groups: the graphic and propositional subjects (design, urban planning and drawing) and the non-graphic ones (the rest). This distinction has been the classic way of organizing the degree in the different curriculums since the 19th century, and it seems to be ratified at the level of

quantitative results, despite the rigid polytechnic structures in which the ETSAB has been circumscribed since the 1970s. Therefore, the PBL associated with workshop subjects condition not only the learning-teaching methodology, but also the type of grades.

Third, we can also observe in Fig. 6 that if we analyze the distribution of grades of the 6 clusters, and more specifically in the graphic-propositional block, the projects and drawings subjects of the first and second years (Design I-IV, Geometry I-II, Sketching I-III) have the lowest grades. From the second year onwards, the grades are not always lower in the workshop subjects, as is the case at the beginning. The process of adapting to the PBL of the students can explain this progression and suggests the necessity to reinforce university orientation that previous studies also pointed out, and even the possibility of establishing a specific admission test that assesses the competencies of the degree and the methodologies of active work developed in design subjects, present in all semesters.

Finally, one might wonder about the hypothetical results that a parallel study would generate in post-Bologna ETSAB study plans, such as the 2010 and 2014 curriculums. The research question would focus on whether the implementation of ECTS credits has had an impact on the correlation of grades between the different core subjects of the degree (which continue to have a very diverse nature); or if the pre-university training and the new pre-entrance models of recent years have led to greater preparation to enter Architecture, and therefore the first and second grades are no longer the lowest of all studies.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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LEARNING AND PROGRESSION IN (TOO MUCH OF?) AN ENTREPRENEURIAL CHALLENGE DURING COVID-19

D.H. Haneberg¹

Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management, NTNU
Trondheim, Norway
0000-0002-6450-8546

S. Solvoll

Nord University Business School
Bodø, Norway
0000-0002-1272-022X

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ABSTRACT

A venture creation programme (VCP) is an academic programme in which students' creation of a new entrepreneurial venture is a central vehicle for learning. A VCP puts students in the role of entrepreneurs with real opportunities and challenges. The entrepreneurial journey is a bumpy ride, and COVID-19 has added significant challenges for entrepreneurs, including students in VCPs. Previous research emphasises how entrepreneurial learning occurs through handling entrepreneurial challenges. The purpose of the present paper is to investigate the role of COVID-19-induced challenges in VCP students' learning. We applied fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) to data from students in a technology-oriented VCP in Scandinavia, collected in April 2021. FsQCA offers the opportunity to investigate complex logic combinations of factors that explain an outcome and is particularly suited for small samples. Multi-item measures assessed (1) the progress of students' ventures, (2) entrepreneurial learning and (3) perceived challenges from COVID-19. We also asked whether students had entered or exited an entrepreneurial project and whether these projects were run by a team or only the individual student. We found that COVID-19-induced challenges impeded VCP students' learning and that students' individual progress was important for learning during crisis situations. Thus,

¹ Corresponding Author: D. H. Haneberg, dag.haneberg@ntnu.no

entrepreneurship educators should help students get 'back on the horse—which means being involved in new entrepreneurial projects—if their challenges lead them into stagnation and inactivity. Progress, both in students' ventures and for students as individuals, should be nurtured by entrepreneurship educators.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liguori and Winkler [1] emphasised the impact of the pandemic on teaching practices in entrepreneurship education, as entrepreneurship educators worldwide are transitioning from physical 'offline' to virtual 'online' teaching practices. However, developments in entrepreneurship education have also moved towards not only facilitating students' learning about entrepreneurship in the classroom but also learning through actually undertaking entrepreneurship [2], feeding the growth and interest in practices for experiential entrepreneurial learning [2,3], action-based entrepreneurship education [4] and courses and programmes in which students create their own ventures as an integrated part of their education [5,6].

A venture creation programme (VCP) is an academic programme in which students' creation of a new entrepreneurial venture is a central vehicle for learning. A VCP puts students in the role of entrepreneurs with real opportunities and challenges. The entrepreneurial journey is a bumpy ride, and COVID-19 has added significant challenges for entrepreneurs, including students in VCPs. Previous research emphasises how entrepreneurial learning occurs through handling entrepreneurial challenges [7] and even failures [8]. In this respect, COVID-19 could be expected to foster significant learning for student entrepreneurs in a VCP, and recent research has found that entrepreneurs learn from crisis experiences during the pandemic [9].

However, the adversity presented by COVID-19 may also lead entrepreneurs to pursue reactive and protectionist strategies [10], meaning that activities may halt, which may negatively impact entrepreneurs' learning processes. Therefore, the present paper argues that when 'real-world' entrepreneurial activity [3] is introduced as an essential part of the educational process, the potential impact of crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic is likely to go far beyond the transition from offline to online education. Being part of local, regional and even global business life, student entrepreneurs are direct subjects of abrupt restrictions put on their businesses, customers, partners, financiers and stakeholders. The purpose of the present paper is thus to investigate the role of COVID-19-induced challenges in VCP students' learning.

The next section develops a research model for the present paper, outlining factors that are expected to influence students' learning in VCPs. The research model is empirically investigated using questionnaire data from students in a technology-oriented VCP in Scandinavia. Fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) is applied for data analysis. The present paper contributes to entrepreneurship education research by suggesting that learning from failure should be followed by new entrepreneurial endeavours [8] and by pinpointing that learning through being active in a new venture is essential for entrepreneurial learning [5]. Moreover, the present paper relates to developments in challenge- and problem-based engineering education [11].

2 FRAME OF REFERENCE: LEARNING IN STUDENT VENTURES

Learning is central to all entrepreneurship [12], and entrepreneurial learning has emerged as a core concept in entrepreneurship research over the last few decades. In essence, entrepreneurial learning can be understood as the process through which experiences from entrepreneurship are transformed into knowledge that informs future entrepreneurial actions [13]. Entrepreneurial learning builds on experiential learning theory [14]; hence, being involved and active in a new venture is a key factor for entrepreneurial learning [7]. Learning also occurs in situations that are detrimental or even fatal to a new venture, such as different degrees of failure [8]. Thus, the event of entering or exiting a new venture is considered relevant for explaining entrepreneurial learning.

Since entrepreneurial learning is seen as the process informing new entrepreneurial action that is developed or improved over time [14], progress in a new venture is also relevant for entrepreneurial learning. The new venture's progress is a sign that entrepreneurial learning has occurred in the past and that new situations, tasks and challenges are presented to the entrepreneur, which, as mentioned, is key to entrepreneurial learning [7]. Hence, new venture progress is to be considered relevant for explaining entrepreneurial learning. Experiences of challenges in the entrepreneurial process, such as the crisis situation represented by COVID-19 [9], are also relevant for entrepreneurial learning, and challenges from COVID-19 are therefore considered relevant for explaining entrepreneurial learning alongside new venture progress.

The four factors found to be relevant in explaining entrepreneurial learning—challenges from COVID-19, new venture progress, entrepreneurial entry and entrepreneurial exit—may be combined in a research model, as presented in Eq. (1). The research model states that entrepreneurial learning can be expressed as a function of the four abovementioned factors.

$$\text{entr. learning} = f(\text{challenge, venture progress, entr. entry, entr. exit}) \quad (1).$$

The next section explains the research methods applied to empirically investigate the research model presented in Eq. (1).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research context and data collection

This research builds on empirical data collected from a cohort of students in a technology-oriented VCP in Scandinavia. The VCP is a two-year MSc programme and includes courses in strategy, business management, engineering and social sciences, alongside the facilitation of students' venture creation processes. In April 2021, we

collected our research data through an online questionnaire administered to students in the VCP. Twenty-seven students responded to the survey, representing a 73% response rate. The following paragraphs explain the measures we used in the survey and how we proceeded with the data analysis.

3.2 Sample and measures

Multi-item measures assessed (1) entrepreneurial learning, (2) challenges experienced from COVID-19 and (3) progress of students' ventures. We also asked whether students had entered or exited an entrepreneurial project and whether these projects were run by a team or only the individual student.

Entrepreneurial learning was measured using four items adapted from Funken et al. [15] and rated using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 = Not at all and 7 = To a very large extent. The questionnaire items were: 'In the last year, I have...' (a) '...learned to develop and implement business strategies', (b) '...developed my capability to make a great deal of progress towards building a viable business venture', (c) '...learned to run the new venture more effectively' and (d) '...learned to read the signs of whether the new venture has difficulties'.

Challenge from COVID-19 was measured using a custom-made scale for the present paper, since the COVID-19 pandemic represents a unique and novel situation. For each item, the respondent was asked to answer using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 = Not at all and 7 = To a very large extent. The questionnaire items were: 'In the last year, the pandemic has given me problems in relation to...' (a) '...discussing with others in the study programme', (b) '...participating in lectures', (c) '...communicating with my new venture team' and (d) '...getting/keeping in touch with customers and partners'.

New venture progress was measured using three items adapted from Funken et al. [15] and rated using a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 = Not at all and 7 = To a very large extent. The questionnaire items were: 'In the last year...' (a) '...the new venture has made good progress', (b) '...the likelihood for new venture success has been enhanced' and (c) '...the new venture has developed substantially'.

Entrepreneurial entry was measured with yes/no (yes = 1) alternatives to the question, 'In the last year, I have started or involved myself in at least one new venture'. Entrepreneurial exit was measured with yes/no (yes = 1) alternatives to the question 'In the last year, I have exited at least one new venture'. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Measure	Chro.a	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.	FNT	CP	FMT
Entrepreneurial learning	0.91	4.78	1.56	2	7	2.75	4.60	6.25
Challenge from COVID-19	0.83	4.14	1.32	2	7	2.75	4.00	5.25
New venture progress	0.96	4.35	2.05	1	7	1.33	4.66	6.33
Entrepreneurial entry	–	0.79	0.41	0	1	–	–	–
Entrepreneurial exit	–	0.42	0.50	0	1	–	–	–

SD=standard deviation, FNT=full non-membership threshold, CP=crossover point, FMT=full membership threshold [19]

3.3 Fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis

To be consistent with the research model, we included only students who were involved in a start-up, and three responses were thus removed from the sample. We applied fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) to analyse our data. FsQCA offers the opportunity to investigate complex logic combinations of factors that explain an outcome and is particularly suited for small samples [17]. The package ‘fuzzy’ by Longest and Vaisey [18] was used in STATA/MP version 17.

FsQCA requires that values of all variables range from 0 to 1, where 1 represents ‘full membership’, meaning that a condition is fully in place, and 0 the opposite. While already dichotomous variables are ready for fsQCA, Likert-scale variables need calibration before analysis. We used the direct approach described by Ragin [18]. The values for full non-membership thresholds, crossover points and full membership thresholds are presented in Table 1. Solution consistencies indicate a well-fit model (solution consistency > 0.9).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the fsQCA are presented in Table 2, which reveals three sets of how the included factors combined explain students’ entrepreneurial learning or the absence thereof. One set (Set 1) explains entrepreneurial learning (Entr.learn = 1) and two sets (Sets 2 and 3) explain the absence of entrepreneurial learning (Entr.learn = 0).

Table 2. Truth table from the fsQCA

Set	Chall.	Vent.prog.	Entr.ent.	Entr.exit	Entr.learn.	R.Cov.	U.Cov.	S.Con.
1	0	1	1	1	1	0.192	0.192	0.901
2	1	0	0	–	0	0.149	0.094	0.916
3	1	–	0	1	0	0.055	0.000	0.982

R.Cov.=raw coverage, U.Cov.=unique coverage, S.Con.=solution consistency. ‘1’ means that a factor is present, ‘0’ means that a factor is absent and ‘–’ means that the factor is not relevant in the set.

Using the notation from the research model in Eq. (1), the solution leading to entrepreneurial learning in Set 1 (in Table 2) may therefore be expressed as in Eq. (2). ‘~’ denotes the inverse of a condition, which is the absence of a factor.

$$\text{entr. learning} = \sim\text{challenge} * \text{venture progress} * \text{entr. entry} * \text{entr. exit} \quad (2).$$

Similarly, the solutions leading to the absence of entrepreneurial learning in Sets 2 and 3 (in Table 2) may be simplified to Eq. (3).

$$\sim\text{entr. learning} = \text{challenge} * \sim\text{entr. entry} * (\sim\text{venture progress} + \text{entr. exit}) \quad (3).$$

Eq. (2) shows that new venture progress and entrepreneurial entry and exit, as well as an absence of pandemic-induced challenges, were necessary for entrepreneurial learning. Using Eq. (3), we found that pandemic-induced challenges and the absence of entrepreneurial entry were necessary for the absence of entrepreneurial learning. Entrepreneurial exit during the pandemic hindered entrepreneurial learning. Additionally, either the absence of new venture progress or entrepreneurial exit completes the two pathways that explain the absence of entrepreneurial learning. Thus, one finding of the present paper is that all four factors in the research model in Eq. (1) were relevant for explaining entrepreneurial learning.

Even though fsQCA operates with the existence or non-existence of an outcome, entrepreneurial learning is, in practice, not either-or but rather relatively more or less learning. Thus, the results suggest that the combination of factors on the right side of Eq. (2) facilitates entrepreneurial learning, while the combination of factors on the right side of Eq. (3) prevents entrepreneurial learning. Challenges from COVID-19 are therefore found to counteract entrepreneurial learning to some degree, while new venture progress, as expected, facilitates entrepreneurial learning. Interestingly, the combination of entrepreneurial exit and entrepreneurial entry, in addition to progress in the new venture, was found to be necessary for entrepreneurial learning. Assuming that the progress is in the new venture that was entered, this finding points to some interesting dynamics. For instance, some ventures may be severely impacted by COVID-19, to the point that a student entrepreneur chooses to exit that venture. However, the process of experiencing and handling that process could potentially facilitate the student’s learning. In contrast, a lack of new venture progress or entrepreneurial exit without entrepreneurial entry (see Eq. (2) and Eq. (3)) did not facilitate learning to the same degree, given that the student had experienced high levels of COVID-19-induced challenges.

The present paper cannot prove causality between, for instance, new venture progress and entrepreneurial exit or entry, between COVID-19-induced challenges and new venture progress, or between COVID-19-induced challenges and entrepreneurial exit. Thus, there may be processual dynamics that can provide clearer models and conceptualisations of how crisis-induced challenges influence the entrepreneurial learning of students in VCPs. However, the results of the present paper suggest that

while challenging events such as exiting and entering a venture facilitate learning as long as there is progression in the new venture, challenges combined with stagnation prevent learning. Not only is new venture progress important for entrepreneurial learning in VCPs, but also progression for individual students. In other words, it is important that VCP students get 'back on the horse' during a challenging situation to avoid passiveness and stagnation. For action-based entrepreneurship education in which students learn through entrepreneurship, faculty should be aware of how active progression for the individual student is important for learning and ensure that students who experience difficulties handle those difficulties within their current venture or choose to become part of another venture in which progress can be made and experienced. Faculty providing challenge- and problem-based engineering education should balance the levels of challenges that students are exposed to, strive for some degree of progression and help students avoid too much stagnation in the activities and projects they are involved in [11].

5 SUMMARY

The purpose of the present paper was to investigate the role of COVID-19-induced challenges in VCP students' learning. Through an empirical study of students in a technology-oriented VCP in Scandinavia, the present paper found that COVID-19-induced challenges prevented VCP students' learning. Interestingly, the findings of the present paper further suggest that students' individual progress was important for learning during crisis situations. An implication for entrepreneurship educators is to help students get 'back on the horse'—involved in new entrepreneurial projects—if challenges in the current venture lead to stagnation and inactivity. The adversity presented by COVID-19 is an example of what could present too much of a challenge for VCP students. The present paper therefore contributes to entrepreneurship education research by suggesting that learning from failure should be followed by new entrepreneurial endeavours [8] and by pinpointing that learning through being active in a new venture is essential for entrepreneurial learning regardless [5].

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